

PROCESSING OF POLYETHYLENE INTO HYDROCARBON FUELS BY CATALYTIC CRACKING ON PILLARED INTERLAYERED CLAYS (PILC)**Stolyarova I.,***Dumanskii Institute of Colloid Chemistry and the Chemistry of Water, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, (Kiev, Ukraine)***Kushko A.,***PhD in Chemistry**<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7946-3419>***Prihod'ko R.***Doctor of Chemical Sciences, National Technical University of Ukraine "Ihor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute", Senior Researcher (Kyiv, Ukraine), ORCID:: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8999-8898>**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11087907>***Abstract**

Catalytic cracking of polyethylene on modified montmorillonite and saponite, and their regenerated samples in a batch reactor was studied. Columnar clays are capable of almost completely converting polyethylene into gaseous and liquid hydrocarbons, exhibiting a low coking level. The selectivity and yield of liquid hydrocarbons were high, since the mild acidity of the columnar clays made it possible to avoid excessive cracking to small molecules. Samples of the regenerated catalyst showed a slight loss of conversion level and selectivity with fresh clay samples.

In addition, they gave hydrocarbons with almost the same distribution as fresh samples, which confirms the possibility of complete regeneration of columnar clays. Both the high yield of liquid products and the ability to regenerate make PILC potential catalysts for industrial use.

The influence of the heating rate on the quality and distribution of the liquid product is also investigated using different heating temperatures. This result shows the importance of the state of the polymer at each stage of the pyrolysis process.

Keywords: Pillared clays; Catalytic pyrolysis; Mixed plastics; Feedstock recycling

Introduction

The problem of cross-linked polyethylene waste processing is becoming more and more urgent every year. A huge amount of plastic waste, which was formed as a result of a sharp increase in the production of polymers, causes serious environmental problems, since plastic does not decompose and remains in municipal landfills for decades. Currently, more than 40% of the entire plastics market is accounted for by polyethylene. Polyethylene is the most widely distributed due to its relatively low cost and easy processing of polyethylene products. The thermal effect on the cross-links in the polymer is carried out in the processes of thermal or thermocatalytic cracking of cross-linked polyethylene, which leads to the formation of liquid products, however, it should be noted that the selective effect on the cross-links in polyethylene by means of these approaches is difficult to achieve due to the presence of various competing reactions of breaking the polymer chain. As a solution to this problem, the processing of polymers in various ways was proposed. Among them, the thermal or catalytic degradation of plastic waste into fuel demonstrates the highest potential for a successful future commercial process of polymer processing, especially since we can consider plastic waste as a cheap source of raw materials in times of accelerated depletion of natural resources.

Since pure thermal decomposition requires relatively high temperatures, and its products require further processing to improve their quality, catalytic degradation of plastic waste has significant advantages of further processing.

For such a process of catalytic cracking, the catalysts previously used mainly based on zeolites have two serious disadvantages. They have a very narrow pore size distribution, in the range of micropores, and have strong acidity. It is possible to assume that the polymer is destroyed first of all on the outer catalytic surface and only small fragments can penetrate into the porous structure of the catalyst for further interaction. On the surface of the zeolite, this destruction takes place mainly to small molecules, increasing the output of gaseous hydrocarbons, which are considered lower compared to liquid fuel due to the complexity and cost of their transportation.

In search of suitable catalysts for plastic catalytic cracking, we introduced columnar clays, which have a much milder acidity than zeolites and have a bimodal pore structure, including micropores (< 0.8 nm) as well as mesopores.

Pillared clay (PILCs) are attracting increasing attention from researchers due to their potential to be used as effective catalysts and adsorbents. However, the technological design of the process for obtaining these promising microporous materials is complicated due to two circumstances. First, laboratory methods for the synthesis of columnar clays have been developed on the basis of natural sodium bentonites or specially prepared Na-forms of montmorillonite, the rock-forming mineral of bentonite clays [2, 3]. Unfortunately, there are very few sodium bentonite deposits in the world. The overwhelming number of industrial bentonite deposits, including all deposits in Ukraine, are calcium formations. Obtaining pure sodium forms from

them is a lengthy and energy-intensive process that requires the use of high-speed centrifuges for repeated washing of highly dispersed Na-montmorillonite from excess electrolyte.

Secondly, in laboratory conditions, researchers, as a rule, operated with low-concentration aqueous dispersions of sodium montmorillonite and dilute solutions of basic salts of polyvalent metals. The low ratio of solid:liquid phase (S:L) makes it difficult to design the process of producing columnar clays as an effective technology. Therefore, researchers are faced with the task of developing a method for producing columnar microporous sorbents based on calcium bentonites using more concentrated solutions and dispersions of reagents. This is the purpose of this work.

One of the barriers to commercialization of PILC clay reaction processes is their low thermal stability, which leads to the destruction of their structure during regeneration, and this work investigates the regenerability of PILC clay catalysts.

This work reports on the catalytic cracking of polyethylene on pillared clays, pillared aluminum montmorillonite PILC-M, and pillared aluminum saponite PILC-S, as well as their regenerated samples. The influence of heating rate and duration on the quality and distribution of liquid products of the pyrolysis process is also studied.

Experimental section

Materials. Powdered columnar clay samples PILC-M and PILC-S (particles $<160 \mu\text{m}$) were used as catalysts in this study. They were synthesized from their parent clays, montmorillonite (M) of the Pyzhevskoye deposit with the general formula $(\text{Ca,Na})(\text{Al,Mg,Fe})_2(\text{OH})_2[(\text{Si,Al})_4\text{O}_{10}] \times n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Ukraine) and, saponite (S) of the Tashkovsky deposit with the general formula $\text{Ca}_{0.25}(\text{Mg,Fe})_3(\text{Si,Al})_4\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2 \times n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Ukraine), respectively, in accordance with the procedure described in detail [3]. For PILC-S, the specific surface area was determined to be 220 ($10 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), and the d001 distance was 1.82 (0.02 nm) to 1.82 (0.03 nm). After experimenting with fresh samples, the coke formed on columnar clay catalysts were burned at 823 K, and the regenerated columnar clay clays were used as a catalyst for the same process. Unstabilized linear low density polyethylene (PE), number average molar mass 117 kg/mol, in powder form (average particle size approx. $100 \mu\text{m}$) was used as a model raw material.

Preparation of the Al-clay catalysts

For the study, we took a specially prepared Ca-form of Pyzhevsky montmorillonite with a cation exchange capacity of $E = 1.05 \text{ mg eq/g}$, Tashkovsky saponite $E = 0.68 \text{ mg eq/g}$ and PEG from Merck (Germany) with a molecular weight $M = 40000$. The Ca-form of the clay mineral sample was added to a 1-2% aqueous solution of PEG with stirring in an amount ensuring a solid:liquid ratio = 1:20. The contact time between clay and PEG solution with periodic stirring was 24 hours. This time ensures that adsorption equilibrium is achieved. After settling the dispersion and removing the sediment solution by decantation and short-term centrifugation, the concentration of the solid phase in the sediment was 14-17%.

Modifying solutions with cations $[\text{Al}_{13}\text{O}_4(\text{OH})_{28}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_8]^{3+}$ (Al_{13} -cations) were prepared by adding a NaOH solution to a 0.2-0.5 M solution of $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ at room temperature and vigorous stirring until pH 4.72 and OH ratio $-/\text{Al}$ equal to 2.56. The resulting mixture was kept for 3 hours at 323K. Then the modifying solution was added dropwise to a 14-17% clay dispersion with vigorous stirring until the ratio $\text{Al}/\text{clay} = 2.5 \text{ mmol/g}$. The resulting mixture was kept for 3 hours at 353K. The synthesized product was separated from the mother liquor by centrifugation, washed with deionized water and dried at room temperature.

The last stage of obtaining columnar montmorillonite was firing it at 773K and the rate of raising the furnace temperature from room to a given 1K per minute. After reaching 423K, firing was carried out in a stream of air to remove PEG from the resulting sorbent. The duration of firing of the sorbent at 773 K was 5 hours, of which in the first hour the firing was carried out in a stream of air. Subsequently, cylinders measuring $4 \times 6 \text{ mm}$ were formed from the resulting modified catalyst.

Analytical methods

Structural and adsorption studies of the resulting columnar sorbent were carried out in parallel with the study of natural Pyzhevsky montmorillonite, as well as columnar clay obtained from the Na sample using a generally accepted method.

X-ray diffraction analysis of PILC and its precursor was carried out using a diffractometer Rigaku RINT-2000 ($\text{CuK}\alpha$ - radiation, Ni filter) in the Bragg angle range $(2\theta) 1.5\text{-}60^\circ$ and scanning speed $1^\circ/\text{min}$.

Nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms (at 77 K) on samples previously evacuated at 473 K for 5 hours were obtained using a Micromeritics ASAP 2010 adsorption unit. The BET specific surface areas (S_{BET}) were determined by the multipoint model, using the Keii-Rouquerol criteria to find the best linear BET fitting. The pore size distribution was found by processing desorption isotherms using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda method (BJH). [9]

Apparatus and the analyses of products.

The experimental setup consisted of a semi-batch reactor, which was heated by two semicircular infrared heating elements connected to a programmable temperature controller. The following standard temperature program was used, including a linear increase in temperature. After the reactor reached a temperature of 673 K, the system's automation maintained this temperature for 10 hours. This temperature program was sufficient for complete degradation of polymer samples with all catalysts used.

Liquid products were collected in three cooling traps placed in an ice bath (273 K) and connected to the reactor. The volume of gas reaction products formed was determined with a gas flow meter. A two-way stopcock allowed three separate liquid samples to be collected in different cooling traps, one for each cooling temperature phase. Liquid products were analyzed on an Agilent HP-6890N gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (FID) on a quartz capillary column CPSil PONA ($100 \text{ m} \times 0,25 \text{ mm}$). GC/MS analyses of

oil were conducted on a GC/MS (HP 6890N II GC interfaced to HP 5973 MS). GC retention time and mass spectral library search were used for the identification of most resolved peaks in each sample. Identified peaks were classified into n-paraffin, iso-paraffin, olefin, naphthene and aromatic groups, and the weight of each peak was determined by the response factors generated from the four point calibration curves.

After experimenting with samples of cokes formed on columnar clay catalysts fired at 823K, the regenerated columnar clays were used as a catalyst for the same process.

Yield of liquid product was determined by dividing the collected material by the weight of feeding plastic. Yield of residue was determined by adding the difference of catalyst weight before and after reaction to

the weight of residue deposited on the inner wall of the reactor. Yield of gas was not determined during the experiment, but was estimated by the difference of the weight of feeding plastic and the total weight of liquid and residue.

Experimental equipment.

The experimental setup consisted of a batch reactor fig.1, which was heated by gas burners connected to a programmable temperature controller. The linear rate of temperature rise in the reactor was used. The reactor heating rate was 5°/min. up to 673 K. The thermolysis process was carried out for 8 hours. This temperature program turned out to be sufficient for complete degradation of polymer samples with all catalysts used and without a catalyst.

Figure 1. Experimental installation catalytic cracking of polyethylene.

The reactor was purged with nitrogen at a rate of 500 ml/min determined by the mass flow controller to remove volatile reaction products from the reactor in which the molten polymer decomposed.

Liquid products were collected in air- and water-cooled cooling traps. Liquid products were analyzed on a Shimadzu 8A gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (FID) on a CPSil PONA fused silica capillary column (100 m × 0.25 mm i.d.).

Gaseous products were passed through a gas meter and collected into valved gas sampling bags every hour, and analyzed using a Shimadzu 8A gas chromatograph equipped with an FID detector using PLOT-Al₂O₃/KCl (3 m × 3 mm). etc.) column.

The polymer-to-catalyst mass ratio was kept constant at 10 in this study, which resulted in no significant change in the degradation behavior for the polymer-catalyst mass ratios.

Typical amounts of dry catalyst and polymer were 0.5 kg and 5 kg, respectively.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of Al-PILC clay modifications is the most widely described in scientific practice. An oligomer composed of thirteen aluminum atoms [Al₁₃O₄(OH)₂₄(H₂O)₁₂]⁷⁺, call it known as the Al13 polycation, which most often vicorizes in the intercalation of clays. Isolated parts in the interspherical space can be seen as an ultra-dispersed hydroxoaluminum phase, which represents a circular model of the oxide Al₂O₃.

The process of intercalation of Ca-form montmorillonite at a temperature of 323 K with aluminum sol for 3 hours made it possible to extract PILC with enhanced textural properties and material, resulting in high thermal stability [10, 11].

The developed method for extracting clays based on the ion-exchange Ca-form of montmorillonite is based on the first treatment with water and polyethylene glycol (PEG). Macromolecules of this nonionic polymer penetrate into the intersphere spaces of the mineral, coagulating complexes with exchange cations like [12]:

X-ray diffractographs of Ca-form saponite and montmorillonite and samples of these clays modified with A113 cations are shown in Fig. 2. It is clear from

them that the modified clays have all the basal reflexes characteristic of spherical clays with large first basal beatings, which is a characteristic feature for PILC.

Figure 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of original and modified pillared catalysts

The interspherical gap as a result of PEG adsorption on the inner surface of Ca-montmorillonite becomes equal to $\Delta d = 2.04 - 0.94 = 1.10$ nm, d 2.04 nm - basal diffractography shows area d_{001} , which indicates the sum of thicknesses of the first ball and inclusion: Ca-montmorillonite + PEG [13, 14], 0,94 nm - quality of aluminosilicate ball with montmorillonite.

Nitrogen adsorption at 77K of natural clay and intercalated saponins and montmorillonites. The adsorption isotherm of natural clay is type II in the Brunauer,

Deming, Deming, and Teller (BDDT) classification. The adsorption isotherms of the particles intercalated by pillars are brought up to type I in the same classification. Structural power, shown in table 1. Natural clay is characterized by a very low surface area and low pore volume. Intercalation with polycations increases the movement of the fed surface (S_{BET}) As a result, the underground pore volume (V_p) and the volume of micropores of natural clay increase.

Table 1

Characteristics	Montmorillonite	Saponites	PILC-M	PILC-S
$d_{(001)}$ (nm)	0,968	0,98	17,8	16,4
S_{BET} BET surface area (m ² /g)	33	29	271	250
V_p Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	0,019	0.018	0,13	0,09

These results confirm the possibility of obtaining PILC by the proposed synthesis method, based on Ca-montmorillonite from concentrated dispersions and solutions of columnar clay with oligomeric cations introduced into its interlayer spaces.

The conversion was calculated as the mass fraction of the initial polymer sample that reacted with the formation of volatile and liquid products. The rest of the initial polymer turned into coke. Coke in this study is considered carbon deposits at the bottom of the reactor.

In addition to the general values, the output of gas and liquid, as well as conversion values depending on the experimental time, were calculated as follows. The selectivity for the liquid fraction was the fraction of the

evaporated polymer mass converted into liquid products condensed at 273 K, and the output into liquid products was the fraction of the initial polymer sample converted into liquid products.

Figure 3 shows a chromatogram of a sample of polyethylene pyrolysis without a catalyst.

Coke yield was the fraction of the original polymer mass converted to coke formed on the catalyst and was simply equal to: Coke yield = 1-conversion. Calculations were carried out for various time intervals of the experimental procedure, during which liquid and gaseous samples were taken. For each interval, the amount of liquid was determined by weighing. The amount of gas fraction was determined using a gas meter. The absolute amount of each gas sample was calculated based on gas chromatographic analysis.

Figure 3. Chromatogram of the yield of the components of the test sample

The total area of all hydrocarbon gases in the gas sample was divided by the sum of the total areas of all gas samples of the sample under study. The result was the fraction of the mass of this gas sample in the total mass of the gas. The total mass of gas was estimated simply by subtracting the amount of liquid from the mass of evaporated polymer. Finally, the amounts of liquid or gas are divided by the original mass of the polymer. This means that all fluidity values were related to

the initial mass of the polymer. The conversion during each interval was simply the sum of the liquid, gas, and remaining solid yields.

The total conversion of polyethylene into volatile products, selectivity and yield of the liquid fraction, as well as coke yield for samples of fresh and regenerated columnar clay are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Yield of catalytic cracking reaction products on different catalysts.

Catalyst	Yield to gases, (%)	Yield to liquid, (%)	Coke yield (%)
Thermolysis	11	67	22
Freshly prepared catalyst			
Montmorillonite	22	72	6
Saponite	26	69	5
PILC-M	20	76	4
PILC-S	23	74	3
Regenerated catalyst			
Montmorillonite	18	69	13
Saponite	21	68	11
PILC-M	17	75	8
PILC-S	18	72	10

Conversion over both fresh columnar clays was very high, above 95%, and liquid selectivity above 72%. The high final conversion values reflected the fact that coke formation on these catalysts was low and cannot be considered as a measure of catalyst activity. Conclusions about the level of catalyst activity can be made based on the distribution of conversion and yield in different temperature ranges. Liquid products are more valuable than gaseous products and are therefore more desirable than gaseous products.

An important aspect of catalysis on columnar clays is the regenerability of these catalysts. The overall conversion and yield of the regenerated PILC-M were

almost identical to the fresh sample, which means that regeneration of PILC-M is possible and reuse of the catalyst after regeneration results in the same catalyst performance. With the regenerated PILC-S catalyst, the performance was clearly lower than that of fresh PILC-S. Conversion is less than 90%, coke formation is more than 10%. Although the conversion was not as high as the fresh sample, the selectivity for liquid products was maintained at the same level, resulting in a high yield. Therefore, it can be concluded that PILC-S is also regenerable and can be reused, but further research is needed to clarify the aspect of relatively high coke formation for the second time.

Columnar clays are moderately acidic and their active sites require relatively high temperatures to activate in order to degrade the polymer. But higher temperatures simply increased the catalytic activity of the columnar clays without causing excessive cracking activity. The main products of such activities were large enough to be collected in the liquid fraction.

In both cases, the regenerated samples produced liquids with very similar boiling point distributions to their fresh counterparts. This fact is further evidence of the regenerability of columnar clay catalysts for the process under study. Catalytic cracking of plastic on regenerated samples leads to the same quality of liquid

fuel in terms of volatility as on fresh samples. This is consistent with the observed higher coke concentration. The formation of heavier components meant that more coke precursors were formed, resulting in more coke. The yield of C1-C5 hydrocarbon gases is presented in Table 3 for fresh and regenerated PILC.

Alkenes are considered the primary products of cracking. In the presence of strong acidity, they undergo secondary hydrogen transfer reactions, resulting in much lower amounts in the reaction mixture than expected.

Table 3.

Composition of the pyrolysis gas (%).

Catalist	H ₂	CH ₄	CO ₂	CO	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	other
No catalyst	7,1	11,7	12	8	21,3	22,6	11,2	2,9	3,2
Montmorillonite	8,8	10,4	11,8	12,6	19,1	21,2	10,4	2,8	2,9
Saponite	9,2	11,3	12,1	12,4	18,6	20,6	9,8	2,9	3,1
PILC-M	11,2	7,6	12,4	13,5	18,2	21,5	8,9	3,2	3,5
PILC-S	12,3	8,2	12,8	12,3	17,8	22,1	8,9	2,8	2,8
PILC-MR	10,9	7,2	11,8	13,1	18,6	21,8	9,2	3,6	3,8
PILC-SR	11,5	8,6	11,6	12,1	18,1	22,5	9,1	3,3	3,2

The mild acidity of columnar clays does not support secondary reactions and results in the formation of more alkenes in the volatile product distribution. For both columnar clays, butenes were the main gaseous products, followed by C4 and C5. Minor differences were observed between fresh and regenerated columnar clay samples. These data can be explained by the fact that in the first minutes the polymer begins to melt, since in a larger temperature range the polymer undergoes more cracking, therefore, lighter hydrocarbons were produced in greater volumes during this period. In the next interval, the product distribution shifted towards heavier hydrocarbons, and the reason for this could be the new arrangement of the solid structure of the polymer due to cross-linking after reaction at a lower temperature.

Conclusion

A cheap and effective method for the synthesis of PILC cracking catalysts based on natural layered minerals has been proposed.

Due to the importance of catalytic cracking of waste plastics into fuel, natural clays with aluminum pillars, PILC-S, a saponite derivative, and PILC-M, a montmorillonite derivative, were tested for their effectiveness in the catalytic cracking of polyethylene, as well as for their effectiveness after regeneration.

At low temperatures, columnar clay catalysts showed low activity. However, this pattern changes dramatically with temperature, as PILCs are able to completely degrade polyethylene after a slight increase in process temperature. In addition, they achieved high levels of production of liquid hydrocarbon fuels. The yield of liquid products was about 70%. This high liquid yield from columnar clays is due to their weak acidity, which does not withstand excessive cracking to small molecules, and is also reflected in the distribution of the liquid product. In addition, columnar clays produce products that are overwhelmingly in the boiling

range of motor fuels. In addition to the high liquid yield, the low coke yield found in the catalytic cracking of plastic waste on columnar clays makes these materials promising candidates for a future commercial process. In addition, the regenerated columnar clays, after combustion of the resulting coke, showed essentially the same behavior as their fresh counterparts in terms of conversion and yield, as well as product distribution. The regenerative ability of columnar clays increases their potential for successful implementation in a commercial plastic waste cracking process.

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